

A NEW SERIES OF SALTS OF HEXAFLUOFERRIATES

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A series of compounds of the general formula $M'M''FeF_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ (where $M' = K, NH_4, Tl$, etc. and $M'' = Cu, Ni, Zn$, etc.) has been described. The corresponding sodium salts crystallise with four or two molecules of water. The method adopted for the preparation of the corresponding hexafluoroaluminates has been followed for the isolation of these compounds. The sodium salts are highly soluble. The other compounds are also fairly soluble in water. At high temperature or in absence of water, the $[FeF_6]^{3-}$ ion in these compounds seems to break down. These compounds are isomorphous with the corresponding series of hexafluoroaluminates, described previously.

In a previous communication several new compounds of hexafluoroaluminates were described (*this Journal*, 1956, 33, 732). The corresponding compounds of the hexafluoferrate ion are being discussed in the present paper.

Trivalent iron like aluminium gives rise to a series of complex anions with fluorine. The chief amongst these are $[FeF_4]^-$, $[FeF_5]^{2-}$ and $[FeF_6]^{3-}$. Remy and Busch (*Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 961) have made a systematic study of these fluoride complexes of iron and they have shown that the number of compounds isolated and their stabilities depend upon the formation energies of the Fe—F linkages in different groups. The $[FeF_6]^{3-}$ group from this point of view is the most stable one and most of the salts of the complex fluoride ions of iron belong to this group.

Trivalent iron, however, bears a close resemblance to aluminium, and in the latter case, the hexafluoride complexes are more numerous. The present investigation has shown that by suitable choice of the cation, quite a good number of salts of hexafluoferrate anion can be isolated, and in fact, the number of compounds formed by the hexafluoferrate ion now exceeds those formed by the pentafluoferrate ion.

The following series of compounds have been isolated: $M'M''FeF_6 \cdot 6H_2O$ where $M'' = Ni, Zn, Cd, Cu$ etc., and $M' = K, Rb, Cu, Tl, NH_4$ etc.

The corresponding sodium salts in keeping with the schoenite series and the salts of the corresponding hexafluoroaluminate ion, crystallise with four or two molecules of water.

Only a few salts of hexafluoferrate ion were known previously and most, if not all, of them were concerned with the alkali metals. This new series shows an analogy between trivalent iron and aluminium and also offers some scope for the structural study of the hexafluoferrate ion in greater details.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Fluorine in the compounds was determined by fusing an weighed amount of the substance with an excess of sodium carbonate for some time and leaching out the resulting mass with water and filtering the leachate. The amount of fluoride ion in solution was determined as calcium fluoride or lead chlorofluoride. The other constituents in the compounds were determined after removing the fluoride ions completely by heating with sulphuric acid.

Methods of Preparation.—The same methods adopted for the preparation of the corresponding hexafluoroaluminates were followed (*loc. cit.*). Freshly precipitated ferric hydroxide was dissolved in 20% hydrofluoric acid, heated in a platinum basin on a water-bath. A slight excess over the equimolecular proportion of the bivalent metal (e.g., Cu, Zn, Cd, Ni, etc.) in the form of hydroxide, carbonate or basic carbonate was then added to it. A concentrated solution of alkali metal fluoride or bifluoride was added to the solution with constant stirring. On account of the sparing solubility of sodium fluoride in water, a concentrated solution of sodium carbonate was added to the sodium compounds, followed by the addition of an excess of hydrofluoric acid. The solution was filtered and allowed to concentrate at about 80°. When sufficiently concentrated, these were kept in a vacuum desiccator (conc. H₂SO₄). The sparingly soluble alkali metal hexafluoroferrates tend to precipitate down easily. Hence, from time to time the solution was filtered and allowed to crystallise once more. After a few days beautiful crystals appeared. All the compounds belonging to this series formed beautiful crystals; the alkali metal hexafluoroferrates, on the other hand, precipitated down as powder. These beautiful crystals, sometimes coloured, could easily be distinguished when they started to appear at the bottom of the solution. A lower temperature (below 10°) was found to favour the formation of the sodium compounds. At higher temperatures Na₃FeF₆ precipitated down very easily. A slight excess of hydrofluoric acid seemed to favour the formation of these compounds. The following compounds were isolated.

Sodium copper hexafluoroferrate dihydrate.—(Found: Fe, 18.96; Cu, 21.53; F, 38.78. NaCuFeF₆·2H₂O requires Fe, 19.10; Cu, 21.76; F, 38.98%).

Potassium copper hexafluoroferrate hexahydrate.—(Found: Cu, 16.63; Fe, 14.53; F, 29.82. KCuFeF₆·6H₂O requires Cu, 16.70, Fe, 14.67; F, 29.95%).

Ammonium copper hexafluoroferrate hexahydrate.—(Found: NH₄, 5.03; Cu, 17.45; Fe, 15.31; F, 31.36. NH₄CuFeF₆·6H₂O requires NH₄, 5.02; Cu, 17.68; Fe, 15.33; F, 31.71%).

Rubidium copper hexafluoroferrate hexahydrate.—(Found: Rb, 19.43; Cu, 14.81; Fe, 12.91; F, 26.42. RbCuFeF₆·6H₂O requires Rb, 20.03; Cu, 14.89; Fe, 13.08; F, 26.70%).

Thallium copper hexafluoroferrate hexahydrate.—(Found: Tl, 37.16; Fe, 10.11; Cu, 11.33; F, 20.58. TlFeF₆·6H₂O requires Tl, 37.44; Fe, 10.23; Cu, 11.64; F, 20.88%).

Ammonium zinc hexafluoroferrate hexahydrate.—(Found: NH₄, 4.77; Zn, 17.86; Fe, 15.28; F, 31.31. NH₄ZnFeF₆·6H₂O requires NH₄, 4.99; Zn, 18.09; Fe, 15.45; F, 31.55%).

Potassium zinc hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Zn, 16.78; Fe, 14.32; F, 29.36. $\text{KZnFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 17.09; Fe, 14.59; F, 29.81%). Loss in wt. at 110° , 27.89; calc. for the anhydrous compound, 28.26.

Sodium zinc hexafluorferriate tetrahydrate.—(Found: Zn, 19.38; Fe, 16.78; F, 34.18. $\text{NaZnFeF}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 19.79; Fe, 16.91; F, 34.52. Loss in wt. at 110° , 21.03; calc. for the anhydrous compound, 21.81.

Rubidium zinc hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Zn, 15.07; Rb, 19.73; Fe, 12.81; F, 26.50. $\text{RbZnFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 15.24; Rb, 19.94; Fe, 13.03; F, 26.59%).

Ammonium cadmium hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Cd, 27.31; Fe, 13.26; NH_3 , 3.92; F, 13.40. $\text{NH}_4\text{CdFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 27.52; Fe, 13.67; NH_3 , 4.17; F, 13.65%).

Thallium cadmium hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Cd, 18.58; Tl, 34.13; Fe, 9.21; F, 18.82. $\text{TlCdFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 18.89; Tl, 34.36; Fe, 9.39; F, 19.17%).

Rubidium cadmium hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Cd, 23.18; Fe, 11.52; Rb, 17.39; F, 23.46. $\text{RbCdFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 23.62; Fe, 11.74; Rb, 17.97; F, 23.96%).

Sodium nickel hexafluorferriate tetrahydrate.—(Found: Ni, 18.07; Fe, 16.98; F, 34.91. $\text{NaNiFeF}_6 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 18.13; Fe, 17.26; F, 35.23%).

Ammonium nickel hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Fe, 15.15; Ni, 16.41; NH_3 , 4.92; F, 31.88. $\text{NH}_4\text{NiFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Fe, 15.74; Ni, 16.55; NH_3 , 5.09; F, 32.14%).

Thallium nickel hexafluorferriate hexahydrate.—(Found: Ni, 10.62; Tl, 37.48; Fe, 10.08; F, 20.66. $\text{TlNiFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 10.85; Tl, 37.78; Fe, 10.33; F, 21.08%).

General Properties.—These compounds are crystalline and stable under ordinary conditions and turn brown slowly in moist air, due evidently to the formation of ferric hydroxide. These compounds, when left in dry air for weeks, slowly lose water molecules and are transformed to white powders which remain insoluble in water. The compounds lose water rapidly at higher temperature (100°) and are converted to a mixture of metallic fluorides and insoluble fluorferriates of the alkali metals.

Methods of Analysis.—After removal of fluorine by heating the salts with concentrated sulphuric acid, the metals were estimated by following the standard methods of analysis. For the estimation of fluorine, the compounds were fused with sodium carbonate and from the solution fluorine was determined gravimetrically as calcium fluoride.

The sodium salts are highly soluble in water. All the crystalline compounds can be recrystallised from water. In each time, however, some amount of the insoluble alkali metal fluorferriates is precipitated at first.

The crystalline overgrowth of $\text{NH}_4\text{ZnAlF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ on $\text{NH}_4\text{CuFeF}_6 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been observed.

The nature*of link between the fluorine atoms of $[\text{FeF}_6]^{4-}$ group and the divalent metals has been discussed in the previous paper in connection with the hexafluoroaluminates.

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